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EFFECTIVENESS OF WORK CULTURE ON PROJECT PERFORMANCE IN NON -GOVERNMENT ORGANIZATIONS(NGOs): CASE OF ECONOMIC POLICY RESEARCH NETWORK RWANDA (EPRN RWANDA).

BY

Jannet MBABAZI

Reg. No: MBA/PM/21/05/6678

(+250)785972857

Email: mbabazijanet@gmail.com

(Master's Degree in Business Administration with Honors in Project Management submitted to the school of University of Kigali)

Co-supervisor: Dr. Samuel Wabala

Tel: +250 790 394 950

Email: wabsam74@gmail.com

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Abstract

This study aimed at assessing the effectiveness of work culture on project performance in Non -Governmental Organizations (NGOs) with reference to the Economic Policy Research Network (EPRN Rwanda). It was carried out based on three objectives:(i) To ascertain the effectiveness of technology-driven organization's work culture on project performance in Non-Government Organizations, (ii)To determine the effectiveness of short-term contract driven organization's work culture on project performance in Non-Government Organizations, (iii)To assess the effect of Key Performance Indicators (KPI) driven organization's work culture on project performance in Non-Governmental Organization. This study employed a case study design to examine one case of Economic Policy Network Research (EPNR Rwanda). Data were collected using primary and secondary data. The study adopted descriptive and inferential statistics. Questionnaire, interview, and documentary review were the three tools for data collection. Secondary sources were analyzed using descriptive statistics as well as multiple regression analysis. The findings showed that technology-driven organization' work culture, key performance indicators driven organization work culture, and short-term contract driven organization work culture contribute 82.6% on performance of project in NGO in Rwanda. 81.5% strongly agree that, technology driven work culture led to project performance more than physical supervision and 97.6% strongly agree setting targets and commit to achieve should lead to project performance and about 87.9% strongly agree that KPI driven work culture reduces time wastage and promote effective use of resources while 94.4% strongly agree that KPI driven work culture enhances auto evaluation then accelerate efficiency and minimize supervision. Researcher recommended that; there should be a study aiming at assessing technology gap NGO and monitor its daily effective. Finally, NGO should adopt the use of Key performance indicators as monitoring and evaluation strategy to ensure good performance of organization staff.

Keywords: *Non – Governmental Organization, Work culture, Project performance, EPRN Rwanda*

1. Introduction

As so often, every institution needs to innovate activities in order to enhance organizational performance through its different projects. Due to globalization, the world has become a village, and every Non – Governmental Organization (NGO) set a unique work culture that

differentiates working habits from one organization to another. This, however, must be based on the organizational culture. Regularly, companies worldwide change their organizational chart to ensure the structure is flexible enough to accommodate robust processes. Changing organizational culture takes much time and it

takes even lesser time to fall into the trap of mediocrity. A strong culture shapes an organizational decision pattern, guides actions, and drives the individual behavior of all members (Suda, 2017). Understanding and maintaining work culture can have a number of benefits as well as being essential to the success of organizational projects or better performance. On the other hand, if they are not well managed then it can create issues that may negatively impact the project's success (Christopher, 2018).

Ineffective work culture management may result in complications like office conflicts, a drop in productivity, and resource inefficiencies, all of which will have a detrimental impact on the project's performance. The system of a common meaning that members hold that sets an organization apart from other organizations is referred to as organizational culture (Manetje, 2003).

Organizational culture is the particular conventions, values, principles, and methods of acting that work together to give each organization its unique identity. One organization can be distinguished from another by its organizational culture. According to Hofstede (1980), culture is the collective thinking of minds which create a difference between the members of one group from another. As per Schein (1990), defines culture is set of different values and behaviors that may considered to guide to success. According to the Kotter and Heskett (1992), culture means fairly established set of beliefs, behaviors and values of society contain generally. In simple words we can understand that culture is gained knowledge, explanations, values, beliefs, communication and behaviors of large group of people, at the same time and same place.

There are several reasons which explain why work culture is of great importance in the performance of projects of Non -Governmental Organizations in Africa. According to Ozguler (2016), boosting the project's success rate can also be achieved by creating a multicultural project management process employing the procedures that are listed below: Create an organizational cultural map, evaluate the current project management process, come up with an improvement plan, evaluate the organization's level of multicultural competence, evaluate the level of multi-cultural competence of the project managers, develop a multi-cultural project management process, and implement the multi-cultural management process. Sebestyen also looked at other factors influencing project performance, such as stakeholder perception, the human element, and the financial strategy (2017).

According to Mtamba (1971) the beliefs, attitudes, ethics, and values determine the number of results or determine the outputs that come up from the individual engaged in work activity. Further, a positive work culture enhances the productivity and reputation of the business and this promotes customer loyalty which helps the institutions to attract more customers and retain the customer already contracted with the business. A positive and right culture can also help business to retain and attract highly qualified staffs which reduce the unnecessary movement of workers to other businesses and companies which is known as staff turnover (Mwamba, 1971).

African managers adopt "flexible leadership styles" to assure a cross-cultural working environment to leverage the sustainable competitive advantages embedded in cultural diversity (Aluisius Hery Pratono, 2019). Cultural awareness in project management was calculated by asking specific questions about people's experiences and observations. South Africa had an average (68.8%) above the Global Group average (62.6%). Germany (44.1%) had the lowest cultural awareness in project management and Australia (78.1%) has the highest average (Meyer, 2016). Africa's cultural values, political, economic, and organizational contexts have had some influence on project execution. Since they conflict with cultural and professional norms, a number of projects implemented in Africa fail (Abdullahi, 2018).

There is no doubt Non – Governmental organizations play a vital role in improving the livelihood of the population by establishing numerous projects. It is a general belief that Non -Government Organization is the backbone to support the poor and the voice of marginalized people in society (Megersa, Hailu, 2020). A unique way of working lies in what one organization believes and follows which makes them unique. One of the many elements regulating the expansion of Non-Governmental Organizations was thought to be work culture. (Kadozi, 2019).

Indeed, EPRN Rwanda is a Non –Governmental Organization initiated in 2008 and officially registered by Rwanda Governance Board in 2018. The network's goal is to support the development of economic policies that are grounded in evidence by offering top-notch research, enhancing capability, and fostering networking opportunities. EPRN offers its interventions in three areas: capacity building, research, and networking and EPRN with different development partners has established numerous

projects including Female Working on Social Economic Transformation with FES Rwanda and Young Economist Program. Since 2016 with the Ministry of Finance and Economic Planning (MINICOFIN) in collaboration with the GIZ and Investment Policies Programme (MIP) Through the Young Economist Programme (YEP), the Economic Policy Research Network offers a six-month internship to recent graduates with the intention of introducing new perspectives and research skills to the practical environment of economic policy and planning, gaining work experience, and enhancing

1.2. Problem Statement

Institutions are increasingly innovating creativity as a way of paving success of their projects. This is the absolute preference, doable and handy choice since the world is becoming into a global village as a result of globalization. In Rwanda, many Non -Government Organization are directed by distinctive ethical standards together with norms towards work shared by environment and institutions (Daniel, 2016).

In big Non -Government Organizations, executive directors have more challenges in establishing an effective organizational culture, which is an essential element to improve performance and productivity (Kenny, 2006). Work culture and project performance are interdependent and work side to side in institution because the successfulness of an Institution is much depending on the beliefs underlying assumptions and philosophy of both the institution and the environment in general, but this influence change significantly according to the management of the organization or institution and also vary according to the environment or according to the regulatory framework imposed by the government (Daniel, 2016).

These can contribute to a hostile and unpleasant work environment, which can reduce employee loyalty and may worsen problems like harassment, bullying, and high turnover. (McMahon, 2022). due to Uncertainty, inadequate communication, and inconsistency are examples of common corporate culture issues. It takes a lot of work to establish and maintain a distinct workplace culture. Organizational structure, size, composition, industry, and outside restrictions all contribute to this complexity. Many firms have tried to

their applied research skills. EPRN established a unique working culture which include: believe in interns than contracted employees, prefer to outsource consultants than contracted permanent consultants, believe in working with partners and implementing their activities through partners, EPRN built database of members and these are hired in temporary basis in the consultancy assignment won by the organization. Therefore, the present study seeks to assess the effect of work culture to project performance on Non - Government Organization, the case of EPRN Rwanda.

achieve this competitive edge by developing cultures that they label according to the culture they hope to develop. Some organizations have sought to create learning cultures; high performance cultures; service cultures, which should have direct linkages to project performance specifically in non-government organization, complexity lies in employee diversity and external culture (Hunter, 2017).

There is inadequate knowledge that exists by organization about how work culture impacts on the project performance. And specifically, the relationship between short term contract driven organization work culture, technology driven organization work culture and Key Performance Indicators driven organization work culture. Many firms have just started the great task to improve their work culture environment. They are still struggling by the establishment of work environment in the way that clients are well treated to gain customer loyalty and to put the culture at the center of the business targets. (Hunter, 2017).

If the mentioned challenges hindering the effectiveness of work culture on project performance in non-Governmental organization are not handled, will bear more challenges instead. For this, the government in collaboration with international and local NGOs among which the Economic Policy Research Network (EPRN) are found to tackle and keep on working on work culture. Hence, the researcher's intention of conducting this current study was to see whether the NGO can change or improve their work culture to cope with this dynamic world for the purpose of reaching the effectiveness of work culture on project performance in Non -Governmental Organization.

2. Objectives of the study

The main objective of this study is to assess the effectiveness of work culture on project performance in Non-Governmental Organization with reference to the Economic Policy Research Network (EPRN Rwanda). Specifically, this paper has the following objectives:

- [1] To assess the effectiveness of technology-driven organizational work culture on project performance in Non-Governmental Organizations.

3. Research Questions

Research questions are an approach that enables the researcher to specify the issues or problems he/she wants to focus on. They break down the project into more manageable tasks that would need to be investigated and completed. The following are the questions formulated for further investigation:

Q.1. To what extent does technology-driven organizational work culture affect project performance in Non-Governmental Organizations?

4. Concept of Variable

This is about the definition of the main terms of our research topic namely non-governmental organization, work culture, and project performance.

Non-governmental organizations

They are typically non-profit organizations that operate autonomously from the government and, in response to

Work culture

Work culture is largely composed of elements that made up the moral and social ethics of individuals which simply give define the organizations instead of influencing project. Work culture defines as the set of values, attitudes, beliefs, philosophies and underlying assumptions shared through the set of people or organizations and institutions. It should also define a

Project performance

Project performance implies the capability to perform the mission in the efficient and effective way by using

5. Theoretical Review

This part is giving the theories related to effective work culture on project performance in Non-Government Organization;

Theory of excellence

This theory has been developed by Thomas and Robert (2012) and it explains that culture adopted by institution or organization affects its performance and success,

- [2] To determine the effectiveness of short-term contract-driven organization's work culture on project performance in Non-Governmental Organizations.

- [3] To assess the effect of Key Performance Indicators (KPI) driven organization's work culture on project performance in Non-Governmental Organization.

Q.2. How does a short-term contract-driven organization's work culture affect project performance in Non-Governmental Organization?

Q.3. How do the Key Performance Indicators (KPI) driven an organization's work culture affect project performance in Non-Governmental Organizations?

its ambitions, many of them are engaged in humanitarianism or the social sciences (Raju, 2020). NGO's plays an important role in the social development of a state, nation or community and they provide social support that governments are unable or unwilling to provide.

Work culture is made up of shared beliefs, attitudes and perceptions while performance refers to the individual results and outcome measured by using different index and ratios (Campbell, 2010) as the arrangement of different attributes that express an organization (Forehand, Von Gilmer, 1964).

the available resources.

highest performing companies worldwide are known by their culture practices that consider the display actions, the well treatment of customers, the flexibility, the

innovative culture and the good management of resources (Karthikeyan, 2019).

By testing the efficiency this theory has been applied in Nigerian financial institutions and has led to a continuous improvement in innovation, customer care services. It has been chosen to direct this study because different financial institutions in Nigeria have shown the characteristics that lead to improved project performance. Moreover, positive cultural beliefs and standards in an institution especially financial institution contribute to high success. The Excellence Theory, as the first grand theory of public relations,

Goal Setting Theory

Goal-Setting Theory, Given the large number of ways that goals can differ, research has examined how different goal dimensions affect performance. One approach to systematically studying the effects of different goal dimensions is goal-setting theory (Locke and Latham, 2002).

Goal-setting theory is one of the most influential theories in the study of work motivation, describing how goal characteristics influence performance through the mechanisms of attentional focus, effort, persistence, and strategy development. A key finding from goal-setting research is that difficult, specific goals that are accepted result in better performance than do-your-best or easy goals (Locke and Latham, 2002).

Goals assist us to properly focus and work towards achieving the things that are important to us. To efficiently manage one's time, one can apply the Lockean goal-setting principle. This notion is predicated on the idea that having precise and well-defined goals and objectives can increase one's motivation to work harder. This theory states that clear expectations are the only way to achieve great performance. Setting personal goals empowers a person to make plans and, ultimately, live life according to

6. Empirical Review

Project performance refers to the level of achievement of objectives counted in terms of income, non-fixed tangible and intangible assets, sales, and market shares. Project performance implies the capability to perform the mission in the efficient and effective way by using the available resources.

The significant changes work culture that has occurred in financial sector industry have influence the growth of Industries that operate in this sector economies hence non-government organization in Rwanda own more

provides a solid theoretical foundation that explicates the value of public relations to organizational effectiveness at various levels (i.e., program, functional, organizational, and societal) and the factors influencing the values of the public relations, such as organizational structure, environments, culture, power, and individual skills and knowledge (Grunig, J. 2018). In short, the Excellence Theory is resilient to its critics. Nevertheless, the criticisms have generated revisions of the theory and pinpointed areas for moving the theory to the next stage, which will be discussed in the next section.

their own schedule. A person will have a clear understanding of what needs to be done and will be motivated to strive towards the established goals by creating goals that are both demanding and achievable. As a result, they won't waste time on things that won't help them achieve their desired objectives.

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assets either financial asset and fixed non-financial assets. The project performance comes as a result of positive achievement gained by institutions or organizations due to their engagement in work activities that are profitable.

The profit can be described in many forms and this helps the development and the expansion of the industries. Work performance can be achieved by using good and effective management team that make decision on timely basis and who always are aware of

what activities done in an organization. In this scenario, we are dealing with the project performance worldwide that can have achieved when the culture toward activities is regulated in the manner that is comfortable to the work environment.

Top talent is more likely to stay with companies that promote a feeling of community in the workplace. People who are successful in their careers and are aware of the value of their skills frequently quit unpleasant situations where they feel unappreciated and unwanted. Organizational culture results in a positive overall employee experience and a high-performance culture that supports employees' efforts within the company. There is a close relationship between work culture and

7. Conceptual framework

From the discussion provided above, the conceptual framework showed the logical relationship between organizational work culture and project performance. The dependent variable is project performance measured by cost effective, completing on time and attainment of project goals and results. The independent

project performance. Work culture is largely composed of a set of elements that made up the moral and social ethics of individuals which simply give define the organizations instead of influencing the project.

Work culture which should affect project performance are leadership bias and support, cooperation among individuals, familiarity and friendliness, independent professionalism, job satisfaction, and biased practices toward work. Around the word the study that has been carried shows that there is a linkage between the philosophies, habits and underlying assumptions which represent the work culture of institutions and the habits of the environment where the financial institutions are established (Rankin, 2017)

Variable of organization work culture is expected to relate the dependent variable through technology driven, short term contract and key performance-driven. The researcher developed a conceptual model which guided this research shown in the figure 1.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework, 2022
Independent variable (Organization work culture)

8. Materials and methods

The present study was cross sectional. It applied

Descriptive design. Mixed approach employed "Quantitative & Qualitative" the target

population was 174 (154 projects beneficiaries and 12 executive committee). The instruments of data collection were questionnaires technique. Descriptive Statistical method was used to describe the frequency, percentages, and mean and standard deviation of data collected. The correlation coefficient matrix analysis was applied to test the relationship between

variables. Analysis proved that there is a high positive correlation between technology driven organization work culture with project performance and positive correlation between key performance indicators and project performance in non-government organization in Rwanda.

9. Findings and Discussion of the Results

Data were collected through questionnaires addressed to 174 respondents, and documentary review especially the progress of reports on these projects. Data obtained were analyzed quantitatively using computer software of SPSS IBM version 23.0. The participation rate was 100.0% in responding to the questions. In responding to questions and including

descriptive statistical method which was used to describe the frequency, percentages and mean and standard deviation of data collected. this helped research to continue research with editing, coding, classifying and tabulating data with towards the analysis. The study was interpreted in accordance with the study objectives.

Profile of Respondents

Here, the study presents the findings on the profile of respondents including but not limit, gender; Agegroup

of the respondents; educational, background and work experience as detailed in the following tables

Table 1: Study population

Categories of respondents	Total population	Sample size	Sampling method
Executive committee	12	12	Purposive
Active members of these two projects	154	112	Stratified
Total	174	124	

Sampling strategies and sample size

Sample size has been calculated using the formula of

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Granular whereby n is the sample size,

N is the population size and are the margin of error of 5%. Sampling strategy will be purposive. Using the formular, sample size is 124.

Table 2. Gender distribution of the respondents

Gender distribution of the respondents	Frequency	Percent
Male	68	54.8
Female	56	45.2
Total	124	100.0

Source: Field data, 2022

The findings showed that the majority of the respondents were male represented by 54.8% as compared to males' counterpart of females represented by 45.2%. This indicated that more males are participating in the activities of Economic Policy Research Network. As EPRN is a network of researcher; according to the United Nations Educational

Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), women make up of researchers globally, leaving most of research work to men. Though there is no current research showing proportional of women and men researchers in Rwanda but second data shows a difference in numbers. Therefore, there is a still a room for Economic Policy Research to engage more female

in research and aim to have gender diversity in the network as it has initiated and implemented the Female

Working Group which aims to transform females from one step to another good step.

Age distribution of the respondents

Age distribution is a good indicator which orient where an organization should focus in terms of providing the

interventions. The following table 3 shows the age distribution of the respondents

Table 3: Age distribution of the respondents

Age distribution of the respondents	Frequency	Percent
Between 20 and 30 years old	21	16.9
Between 31 and 40 years old	62	50.0
Between 41 and 50 years old	34	27.4
51 and above years old		5.6
Total		100.
	7	0
	124	

Source: Field data, 2022

Table 3 indicates that the majority of the respondents aged between 31 and 40 years old represented 50% followed by those between 41 and 50 represented by 27% while respondents between 20 and 30 years represented by 16.9% and the least represented are those aged above 51 represented by 5.6%. It is significant that executive team, beneficiaries of Female

Working Group and must hold either bachelor's degree, master's degree or Ph.D., and refer to Rwanda perspective, these people are a category of above 30 years of age. During the interview, Female Working Group program coordinator at EPRN said that one of the criteria to recruit beneficiaries of the program includes; having at least a master's degree, and having at least three years of working experience.

Educational distribution of the respondents

Educational background of the people can be one of the indicators of allocating resource and a good way of defining population. Under this study, the researcher

collected data including the education levels of the respondents and findings shown in the following table 4.

Table 4: Educational level of the respondents

Education level of the respondents	Frequency	Percent
Technical skills	11	8.9
Graduate	42	33.9
Postgraduate	71	57.3
Total		
	124	100.0

Source: Field data, 2022

Table 4 indicated that a big proportion of the respondents hold postgraduate degrees representing 57.3% which is significant to the study because one of the important criteria for recruiting beneficiaries of the female working group, to have a master's degree is among the many. This is followed by graduates represented by 33.9% these include a member of the executive team of the program, a few Economic Policy Research Network members, and some of the beneficiaries who fulfill all requirements except having a master's degree. The study revealed that there is a shortage of technical skills holders in the network of

Economic Policy Research Network and following the aim of the network of mobilizing people to come together and share expertise, there is a need for the network to mobilize those with technical skills; moreover, to due to the female working group for economic transformation targets those females with a background in the socio-economic field or who have a profession in these subjects. The researcher recommended Economic Policy Research Network design a project that includes men in the same interventions as the Female Working Group for Economic Transformation

Table 5: Correlations Coefficient Matrix between the variables

Statement		Technology-driven lead to project performance	Short term contract led to project performance	Key performance indicators lead to project performance	Project performance
Technology-driven lead to project performance	Pearson Correlation	1	.540**	.661**	.729**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000
	N	124	124	124	124
Short term contract led to project performance	Pearson Correlation	.540**	1	.532**	.765**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
	N	124	124	124	124
Key performance indicators lead to project performance	Pearson Correlation	.661**	.532**	1	.790**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000
	N	124	124	124	124
Project performance	Pearson Correlation	.729**	.765**	.790**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	124	124	124	124

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: primary data (2022)

From the correlation matrix test on table 5, results show that there is there is positive relationship between technology driven work culture, short term driven work culture and key performance indicators with project performance in non-governmental organizations indicated by 0.72; 0.76 and 0.79 respectively. However, among analyzed variables, Key performance contribute

more among than the rest. Therefore, this recommends similar organizations to consider the role of technology driven work culture, short term driven work culture and key performance as some of the variables that should contribute to project performance.

10. Conclusion and recommendations

Based on the interpretation of collected and analyzed data during this study whereby a researcher was interested to analyze three independent variables which are technology, short contract and key performance indicators as organization work culture with project performance The findings showed that, there is a strong correlation among independent variables with project performance. The study recommended the following;

- [1] There is a need to mobilize other non -government organization to adopt technology and replace manual process in their routine work but monitor how employees use technology
- [2] Researcher recommended non-government organization to adopt the use of Key performance indicators as monitoring and evaluation strategy to ensure good performance of organization staff.

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